

Gravimetric Determination of Gold Using Thiosalicylic Acid

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A method has been developed for the gravimetric determination of 18-100 mg of gold with thiosalicylic acid. Gold(III) is precipitated in 0.1*N* hydrochloric acid solution, the precipitate washed with ethanol and weighed as $\text{HOOC.C}_6\text{H}_4\text{S.Au}$ after drying at 100°-110°. Ni(II), Co(II) and Zn(II) did not interfere. The interference of Fe(III) was eliminated by masking with EDTA.

GRAVIMETRIC determination of gold is mostly done by reducing it to metal and weighing in this form. In several cases, the metal separates out in a finely divided state and thus makes the transference of the metal into the filter difficult. A number of organic reagents such as dimethylglyoxime¹, tetraethyl ammonium chloride², 2 mercaptobenzenethiazole³, and thionalide⁴ were used as complex-formers for the precipitation of gold but unfortunately these precipitates do not have a constant composition and hence need conversion to the metallic state through ignition. Very few organic reagents like thiophenol⁵, sodium salt of *N*-(*N*-Bromo - *C*-tetradecyl - betainyl) - *C*-tetradecyl-betaine⁶, thioglycollic acid⁷, polymethylene ammonium salts⁸, 8-mercaptoquinoline⁹ and *m*- and *p*-phenylene di-(1-tetrazoline-5-thiones)¹⁰ produce organic weighing forms with the advantage of both easy transference and purification. Reinecke salt¹¹ also yields a precipitate which can be directly weighed. Thiosalicylic acid, inspite of its known potentialities as an organic chelating agent, has not been so far used for the determination of gold. The present communication deals with the use of this reagent for the gravimetric determination of gold.

Experimental

Standard gold solution: About 1 g of pure gold was dissolved in aquaregia, carefully evaporated thrice to near dryness with concentrated hydrochloric acid in the presence of few mg of sodium chloride and the gold chloride solution finally made up to a litre while adjusting the acid strength to 0.1*N* in hydrochloric acid. The gold strength was further ascertained gravimetrically^{12, 13}.

Thiosalicylic acid solution: 1 g of the reagent (E. Merck) was dissolved in 100 ml of glacial acetic acid and filtered. The solution remained stable for about a week when kept in a very clean, tightly stoppered bottle.

Recommended procedure: An aliquot of the gold solution was taken in a 250 ml beaker. It was diluted to ca. 100 ml with distilled water and the acid strength adjusted to 0.1*N* with 0.2*N* hydrochloric acid. The solution was boiled and the reagent added slowly with stirring, 1 ml of the reagent being used for every 3 mg

of gold. Excess addition of the reagent should be avoided. The contents were kept over hot water bath for about 2 min. The supernatant liquid was tested for complete precipitation and then filtered through an IG4 filtering crucible. The whole of the precipitate was transferred into the filter with the aid of hot water and the precipitate finally washed with four 25 ml portions of 95% ethanol. The crucible was dried at 100°-110° and the precipitate weighed as $\text{HOOC.C}_6\text{H}_4\text{S.Au}$. The gravimetric factor for gold is 0.5527. Sometimes a final wash with about 20-30 ml of ether will facilitate the complete removal of the last traces of the still adheing organic matter. The precipitate appears white at the time of precipitation, pale yellow on filtering and olive green after drying. Table 1 gives the results obtained in the determination of various amounts of gold.

TABLE 1—GRAVIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF GOLD USING THIOSALICYLIC ACID

Gold taken mg	Gold found mg	error, %
18.62	18.69	+0.38
19.26	19.19	-0.36
23.57	23.58	+0.04
48.15	48.21	+0.12
71.25	71.29	+0.06
81.85	82.15	+0.37
96.30	96.40	+0.10

Effect of acid concentration: Acid concentration greater than 0.1*N* in hydrochloric acid gave high results. It was observed that the precipitate was seriously contaminated with the organic matter and inspite of several washings, their complete removal could not be effected. Similarly, longer digestions resulted in positive errors. Nitric acid interfered seriously.

Determination of the error of the method: Table 2 gives the results of a set of experiments. The standard deviation for the set of single measurements is 0.074mg. and the relative mean error, 0.04%.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF THE ERROR OF THE METHOD

Gold taken mg	Precipitate weight mg	Gold found mg	error % mg
22.50	39.8	22.40	-0.10
22.50	39.9	22.45	-0.05
22.50	40.0	22.51	+0.01
22.50	40.1	22.57	+0.07
22.50	40.1	22.57	+0.07
22.50	40.1	22.57	+0.07

Effect of other metal ions: Gold is associated with metals like copper, iron, zinc, nickel, cobalt, platinum, palladium and tellurium in its alloys and ores. Hence studies were made to know the effect of these metals on the determination of gold using the procedure developed. Varying amounts of the chlorides of these metals were added to the gold solution and the gold content determined in each case as described above. The results recorded in Table 3 indicate that nickel, cobalt and zinc did not interfere with the determination even when they were present in five fold excess. Iron (III) produced an orange yellow precipitate but its interference could be effectively eliminated by masking it with EDTA. Copper, platinum palladium and tellurium yielded black, yellow, red and black precipitates respectively with the reagent and thus interfered. Interference from copper, platinum and palladium was avoided by selectively extracting the gold chloride with three or four 25 ml portions of ethyl acetate from 10% hydrochloric acid solutions^{14, 15}. The combined organic extracts were treated with about 100 ml of 0.1N hydrochloric acid and kept on a steam bath to bring gold chloride back into the aqueous phase and the gold content determined according to the procedure described.

TABLE 3—DETERMINATION OF GOLD IN THE PRESENCE OF SOME FOREIGN METAL IONS.

Gold taken. mg	foreign metal ion added, mg	Gold found mg	error. %
30.00	Co ²⁺ (150)	30.04	+0.13
30.00	Ni ²⁺ (150)	30.16	+0.53
30.00	Co ²⁺ (100) Ni ²⁺ (100)	30.21	+0.70
30.00	Zn ²⁺ (150)	29.98	-0.07
37.50	Zn ²⁺ (200)	37.47	-0.08
30.00	Fe ³⁺ (100) [@]	30.21	+0.70
37.50	Fe ³⁺ (200) [@]	37.70	+0.53

@ EDTA was added.

Mechanism of the precipitation: The mechanism of the precipitation could probably be as follows ;

That the reaction ratio of gold to reagent is 1 : 3 was supported by the potentiometric titration experiments conducted as follows.

A 0.01M solution of the reagent in glacial acetic acid was prepared by accurately weighing the requisite amount of the sample, recrystallised twice from alcohol. An aliquot of this solution was taken in a 150 ml beaker and glacial acetic acid was added to bring the volume to ca.100 ml. It was then titrated with a standard gold solution (0.005M) potentiometrically using a platinum indicator electrode and a saturated calomel electrode (having a sintered disc at the tip). A jump of about 200 mVs marked the equivalence point. This corresponded to a stoichiometry of 1 : 3 (metal : reagent). But the titres were always a little lower than theoretical. When the reagent solution contained about 50% v/v of acetic acid, the titres were still lower. The low titres are thought to be due to the coprecipitation of the reagent along with aurothiosalicylic acid. Titration of gold with the reagent was not possible since it invariably yielded metallic gold, when small aliquots of the reagent were gradually added to the gold solution. This might be due to the oxidation of the reagent beyond the disulphide stage in the presence of excess oxidant¹⁶. Alternatively, aurothiosalicylic acid might slightly be getting dissociated giving rise to Au⁺ ions which in turn disproportionate to Au³⁺ and Au⁰. To verify the latter possibility, a test tube reaction was conducted as follows. A small amount of the aurothiosalicylic acid was treated with gold chloride solution and the mixture was slightly warmed on a hot water bath. It was then centrifuged, washed with water and the precipitate collected was treated with dilute ammonia, which dissolved aurothiosalicylic acid. The insoluble portion was found to be metallic gold.

I. R. Spectra of aurothiosalicylic acid was recorded using KBr discs. The band at 2520 cm⁻¹ corresponding to ν (S—H) stretching vibration in thiosalicylic acid is absent in that of the compound confirming that the sulphhydryl group is replaced by the metal. The carbonyl stretching frequency at 1682 cm⁻¹ in the reagent has not shifted in the spectra of the compound. It can hence be deduced that in the compound the carboxylic group does not enter into coordination.

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